

Cold gas kinematics of star forming galaxies at high-z cluster forming epoch

ISM mass : <https://arxiv.org/abs/1705.10330> (in press)

Kinematics : M. Lee et al. 2017b in preparation

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Outline of this talk

- **Introduction**
- **Protocluster 4C23.56 at $z=2.49$**
- **ALMA observations**
- **ISM mass and gas fraction**
- **Resolved kinematics with gas**
 - unfortunately only one with detailed study,
 - others only from spectral/visual
- **Summary**

'Environmental effect' on galaxy evolution

Formation of Early Type Galaxies

Feeding & Feedback may be more effective in denser environment ?

e.g., Ram pressure (Gunn & Gott 1972), quick gas depletion due to starburst followed by mergers (with structural transformation) (Merritt 1983), strangulation (Peng+2015), tidal interactions (Aguilar & White 1985) and galaxy harassment (Moore +1996)

Recent observations toward high-z (proto)clusters on the main sequence

- Larger gas fraction (accordingly with longer depletion time scale)
- Gas-rich galaxies entered recently into clusters (e.g., Noble+16, Hayashi+17)
- Not for immature cluster cases, i.e., protoclusters ($z > 2$) and those on the MS galaxies
 - only handful cases of starburst galaxies (i.e., above the MS (SFR-Mstar) relation)
 - But these populations are still a small number
 - $z \sim 2$ clusters already have passive galaxies (e.g., Kurk et al. 2009, Strazzullo et al. 2013, Koyama et al. 2014, Cooke et al. 2016)

Protocluster 4C23.56

Contour : MIPS 24 μ m oversensitivity

- 3x overdensity in terms of H α

- ★ **HAE overdensity** (Tanaka+11, Tanaka in prep.) with narrow band technique (seeing-limited)
- ★ **25 HAEs are detected up to now**
- ★ **overlap between (*classical, unresolved*) SMGs with HAEs**

**Focussing on HAEs.
Others have poor
redshift constraints.**

Protocluster 4C23.56

(Jy)

ALMA observations

	1.1 mm (cycle1)	CO(3-2) (cycle2)	CO(4-3) (cycle3)	[CI] (cycle3)
resolution ("x") natural	0.78x0.68	0.91x0.66	0.54x0.33	0.43x0.29
noise level (mJy)	0.08-0.12	0.24	0.16	0.14

at 50 km/s bin

Step 1.
Dusty SF?

Step 2.
**Redshift
confirmation
and gas mass**

Lee et al. 2017 (in press)

ALMA observations FoV

Detection of dust and gas

- 1.1 mm and CO(3-2)
 - for known sources of HAEs
 - 1.1 mm 4/19
 - CO(3-2) 7/22 detection
 - all 1.1 mm with CO(3-2)
- CO(4-3) (among six CO(3-2) targeted)
 - 3/6 $S/N > 5$
 - less massive; $M_{\text{star}} < 1e11 M_{\text{sun}}$
 - 3/6 $4 < S/N < 5$
 - two are $> 1e11 M_{\text{sun}}$

choice of integrating range :
 the line widths that gives the
 highest S/N ~ roughly
 consistent with gaussian fitting
 when the fitting is successful

Gas fraction

- The average f_{gas} within the protocluster (those on the MS) does not differ from field galaxies on the MS (but, slightly higher)
- The scatter of distribution is 13% higher

Changing star formation law?

The changes of SFE as a function of M_{star} is higher than what is expected even with super-linear K-S relation

(but note the scatter and narrow range)

Environmental dependence?

- 5/7 are detected in the densest region (but, projected density)
- These five galaxies show...
 - the dependency of gas fraction not only for Mstar but also the galaxy number density
- **Tendency of higher gas fraction in less denser region and smaller gas fraction in highly dense region (although statistics with large number is necessary)**
 - ✓ due to the change of local SFE?
 - ✓ due to the change of angular momentum? (via merger?)
 - ✓ halo concentration parameter?

$$t_{\text{depl}} = \frac{t_{\text{dyn}}(R_d)}{\eta} = \frac{1}{\eta} \times \frac{R_d}{v_d} = \frac{\lambda R_h}{\eta \times C_h v_h} = \frac{\lambda}{\eta C_h} \times 0.1 H(z)^{-1}.$$

e.g., Mo+98; Genzel+15

Summary

- Detection of gas component in both dust continuum and CO(3-2) (and CO(4-3))
 - while f_{gas} on average is similar to field galaxies,
 - the scatter is tentatively large; (drastic) **change of SFE (at given sSFR) due to environmentally driven mechanism?**
 - **aco may not be universal** (even for those on the main sequence!); may be depending on its physical condition
- Rotating-dominated disks do exist but **frequent mergers** are seen both in CO(4-3) and stellar component when resolved even for massive-end

Final remark : too many diversities with limited sample

- Always it is a problem with a pencil beam study.
 - Environmental dependence and early-formation of ETGs in the early Universe still elusive. Making a concrete conclusion is not simple with the limited sample.
- Larger number of samples (both in massive-end and less massive-end, various 'environment') necessary